

MICROMECHANICS DAMAGE APPROACH TO AN UNIDIRECTIONAL GLASS FIBER COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

A study is conducted to determine the damage mechanisms of an unidirectional composite (E-glass fiber - epoxy matrix) subjected to a tensile load in the longitudinal (fiber) direction. An analytic approach based on Piggott's elastic-slip stress transfer model as well as an axisymmetric finite element calculation are developed for analysing the microstresses in the composite containing an arbitrary number of broken fibers in order to modelize the damage from the main microstructural features (components characteristics, local fiber volume fraction). The results obtained agree well with the experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

One of the new applications of composite materials to the automobile industry is the use of unidirectional fiberglass-reinforced plastics for structural parts like springs. In order to optimize the suspension parts design, it is essential to obtain a good knowledge of the tensile behaviour of such a material. The tensile behaviour of fiberglass-reinforced composite is quite different from that of homogeneous isotropic materials. In homogeneous isotropic materials, the tensile failure process consists of initial crack nucleation and subsequent propagation in a single mode. However, the fiberglass-reinforced composite, even unidirectional, exhibits a variety of failure modes, including: individual fiber fracture, interfacial bond failure, matrix cracking, delamination, etc [1]. In this study, emphasis has been placed on the understanding of the tensile failure sequence and of the corresponding mechanisms. This has been done by means of two damage micromechanic approaches: one is an analytic solution based on Piggott's elastic-slip stress transfer model [2] [3], and the other is a micromechanics modelisation using finite element calculations.

MATERIAL

The material studied is an unidirectional composite consisting of E-glass fibers and epoxy matrix. It is fabricated from prepreg sheet by curing the prepreg with heat (135°C) and pressure (5 bars) for 2 hours. The average fiber content of the composite obtained is about 50% by volume. This composite is of good quality which can be proved by its excellent mechanical properties as shown in Table 1. By microscopic examination, however, it was found that this composite contains some defects, including: fiber faults which are the main cause of fiber premature fracture [4]; non homogeneous fiber repartition and fiber misalignment. These defects can have significant effects on the failure process of the composite.

FAILURE PROCESS

A large number of static tensile tests was performed on the composite in order to study the failure process and mechanisms of this material. From the analysis by stereo X-ray radiography and from the observations in the scanning electron microscope, it was found that the main damage process in a tensile test consists essentially of four stages:

1. Individual fiber fractures at random locations within the composite. This begins at almost 40% of the ultimate load owing to defects in the brittle fibers [5]. As the load increases, fiber fragmentation and fiber-matrix interface debonding occur.

2. Accumulation of the fiber fractures in a bundle of fibers, forming macroscopic cracks at different locations along this bundle.
3. Initiation of delaminations starting from the macrocracks.
4. Propagation of the delaminations in the fiber direction.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the composite and its two components

	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	σ_{R1} (MPa)	σ_{R2} (MPa)	τ_{R12} (MPa)	A (%)
Unidir. composite	40	10	4	0,30	1000	150	90	2,5
glass fiber E	75			0.22	< 3000			4
epoxy resin	3,45			0.35	65~ 80		30~50	> 7

DAMAGE MODELLISATION BY AN ANALYTIC APPROACH

In order to study the failure process and the corresponding mechanisms of the composite, it is necessary to have a good knowledge of the interaction of broken fibers with their neighbours.

When an unidirectional composite in which the fibers have a much lower fracture elongation than the matrix (Table 1) is gradually loaded in the fiber direction, some fibers can break prematurely at their weakest points [6]. As a result, an interfacial shear stress concentration is built up around the fiber break. When the applied longitudinal stress exceeds a certain value, the interfacial shear stress could reach the interfacial shear strength, and debonding could occur at the interface [3]. In this case, Piggott's elastic-slip stress transfer model can be readily used to analyse the local stress distribution and the interfacial debonding.

As the applied load increases, the individual fibers successively break creating a bundle of broken fibers, which can then lead to longitudinal split at the bundle surface due to shear stress concentration. Therefore, we attempt to develop an analytic approach in order to find an approximate solution for the case of fracture of more than one fiber, that is, a bundle of broken fibers. This approach is in fact an extension of Piggott's elastic-slip stress transfer model.

Fig.1. Model for an unidirectional composite containing N_f broken fibers
 (a) Distribution of the interfacial shear stress without debonding
 (b) Distribution of the interfacial shear stress with debonding

In this approach, we assume that both fibers and matrix behave elastically, and that the fibers are all packed in an orderly fashion. The matrix is assumed to carry only shear stresses and the fibers are assumed to carry only tensile stresses. Load is transferred from the bundle of broken fibers to adjacent unbroken fibers through a layer of matrix by the elastic-slip stress transfer mechanism [2]. The tensile stress in the axial direction is supposed to be uniform across the section. We assume moreover that the number of broken fibers is small enough in comparison with the total number of fibers in a specimen so that the overall stress field is not disturbed by the fracture of the bundle. The section of the broken bundle is supposed to be circular as is shown in Fig. 1.

It was found by analytic calculation that the shear stress at the bundle surface τ_s can be expressed by the following relation :

$$\tau_s = \frac{1}{2} n E_{bl} \epsilon_1 \sinh (nx/r) / \cosh (nL/r) \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Where L is the broken bundle length, r is the radius of the bundle and ϵ_1 is the applied tensile strain. E_{bl} is the longitudinal Young's modulus of the broken bundle which can be considered approximatively to be the longitudinal Young's modulus of the composite when $r \gg r_f$ (fiber radius). n is a function of the material properties, fiber volume fraction and fiber distribution given by:

$$n = \left\{ E_m / E_{bl} (1 + \mu_m) \ln \left(\frac{r+e}{r} \right) \right\}^{1/2} \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

Where E_m and ν_m are respectively the Young's modulus and the Poisson's coefficient of the matrix. e is the thickness of the layer of matrix surrounding the bundle which is taken to be the mean distance from one fiber surface to the center of a adjacent fiber in the composite.

The maximum shear occurs at the bundle end ($x = L$):

$$\tau_{s \max} = \frac{1}{2} n E_{bl} \epsilon_1 \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

When this shear stress reaches the matrix shear strength τ_{mR} , debonding and slip occur at the bundle surface. If we assume that the interfacial friction stress is constant in the slip region, the ratio of the debonded length to the broken bundle length is found to be :

$$m = \frac{E_{bl} \epsilon_1 - 2 \tau_{mR} / n}{2 \mu (\nu_m E_m \epsilon_1 - \sigma_{rt}) L/r} \quad \text{----- (4)}$$

Where τ_{mR} est the shear strength of the matrix. μ is the friction coefficient and σ_{rt} is the residual radial stress which results from differences between the fiber and the matrix contractions during manufacture of the composite.

By means of this approach, both the shear stress concentration at the end of the broken bundle (Equation (3)) and the debonding length (Equation (4)) can be obtained for any bundle size and at any applied tensile stress. In the case of only one broken fiber ($r = r_f$, $E_{bl} = E_f$), we find the same results as in Piggott's model.

Fig.2 shows the tensile stress beyond which interfacial debonding occurs and the debonding length as a function of the number of broken fibers in the bundle, using the following parameters: $L = 40$ mm (half length of the specimen), $\mu = 0,2$ [2], $e = 10 \mu$ (obtained experimentally), $\sigma_{rt} = -30$ MPa [2].

As shown in Fig.2, for the composite containing at least one broken fiber, debonding occurs when the composite is bearing less than 30% of its failure stress. However, in practice the

fracture of fibers was found to take place only when the applied tensile stress exceeded 30% of the composite tensile strength, so theoretically debonding starts as soon as fiber breaking occurs in this composite. This was checked by experiments where the fibers were well spaced. But when the fibers spacing is very small, the failure sequence is different. This will be discussed later.

At constant tensile stress, the debonding length increases with the number of broken fibers. At a given applied tensile stress, if the number of broken fibers in a bundle N_r is known, the debonding length produced at the bundle surface mL can be predicted theoretically by Equation (4), and vice versa. But these theoretical values are overestimated for mL (or underestimated for N_r) because the fiber misalignment, which can greatly increase the resistance to debonding, was not taken into account in this analytic model. When the broken bundle is situated at the surface, the interfacial debonding is called delamination. Experimentally, we found that delaminations usually occurred only when the composite was on the verge of failure, and the delaminations could grow to a greater length when the broken bundle was larger. By means of this calculation, the minimum size of a broken bundle able to produce a given length of delamination at a given applied tensile stress can be predicted. Fig.2 shows the theoretical debonding lengths as a function of the broken number when the applied tensile stress is 1000 MPa (the mean failure stress of the composite), and some experimental results for the minimum broken fiber number obtained from the specimen after failure in a tensile test are also shown in this figure for comparison. We can see that a good agreement exists between the theoretical solution and the experimental results.

Fig.2. Debonding tensile stress and debonding length as a function of the number of broken fibers

DAMAGE MICROMECHANICS MODELISATION BY A FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The analytic solution presented in the preceding paragraph cannot describe the tensile stress concentration effect at the fiber failure site, so that a finite element calculation model was developed in this study to determine the whole local stress field generated by progressive fiber fracture and to analyse the subsequent local fracture events. The model is axisymmetric and consists of a number of parallel, equally spaced fiberglass in the form of hollow cylinder embedded in the matrix, the whole being surrounded by an equivalent homogeneous material (E.H.M.) as shown in Fig.3. The thickness of the hollow glass cylinders is determined so as to keep the fiber volume fraction equal to that in the real composite. The broken fibers are

assumed to be axisymmetric and the number of broken hollow cylinders can be arbitrary. Both the fibers and the matrix are taken to be elastic in this calculation.

As shown in Fig.3, in the case of one broken fiber, two types of stress concentration are created in the vicinity of the broken end: one is the shear stress concentration at the interface (broken fiber/ surrounding matrix) which tends to induce debonding along the fiber surface; the other is the tensile stress concentration in the first unbroken neighbouring fibers which may lead to their fracture. Therefore, once a fiber break occurs, the local failure process can continue by two different fracture modes: the shear fracture at the interface and the tensile fracture in the adjacent fibers.

Fig.3. Axisymmetric model for a unidirectional composite containing one broken fiber.

Fig.4. Effect of local fiber volume fraction on the local stress concentration created by one broken fiber

The fiber distribution in the composite is not homogeneous, and the local fiber fraction can be very different from the average one for the whole composite. This variation in fiber volume fraction affects the local fracture process. By changing the spacing between the

glass hollow cylinders in the model, it is possible to calculate the evolution of the tensile stress concentration in the first neighbouring fibers, and the shear stress concentration at the interface as a function of the local fiber volume fraction. As shown in Fig.4, when the local fiber volume fraction increases (that is, when the fiber spacing decreases), the tensile stress in the first adjacent fibers increases, but the shear stress at the interface decreases. So we can conclude qualitatively that when the local fiber volume fraction is high, the tensile stress concentration plays a dominant role. Otherwise, it is the shear stress concentration that dominates the fracture process. This result agrees well with the experiments. As shown in Fig.5, it was found by microscopic examination in our experiments that where the fibers are closely spaced, the fracture travels from fiber to fiber by the tensile fracture mode, and where the fibers are well spaced, the failure progresses along individual fiber surfaces forming considerable fiber pull out.

Fig.5. Failure surface for an unidirectional composite

CONCLUSION

The analytic approach based on Piggott's elastic-slip stress transfer model allows to describe easily the shear stress concentration effects produced by the fracture of a bundle of fibers and to predict the minimum size of the broken bundle which can produce a given length of delamination in the unidirectional composite. The micromechanics modelisation by finite element analysis allows to determine the whole local stress field in the vicinity of broken fibers and to understand the effect of the variation in local fiber volume fraction on the damage process. It was found that when the local fiber volume fraction is high, the tensile fracture mode plays a dominant role. Otherwise, it is the shear fracture mode that dominates the failure process. The results obtained by these two approaches have been well verified by many microscopic observations and experiments.

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